

Metadata Management in ML Development

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This report summarises selected metadata reporting formats used in machine learning (ML) development pipelines. It summarises the motivations and use-cases of each format, the technical details, such as the properties (i.e. what information is required from the user), and a comparison of the coverage of each format.

Model Metadata

Model cards are structured and standardised documents highlighting information about an ML model. The name model card was coined by Google in 2018 [1]. As many machine learning models can be considered “black boxes”, it is important to highlight a model’s intended use case and known limitations, especially in the case where models are used for automated decision-making. Misuse in these use cases can have oppressive effects on real individuals [2, 3]. Model cards provide such information to the user adding a layer of transparency to the model usage pipeline. A model card typically consists of information regarding the description of the model, providing an overview of its name, its use cases, what it takes as input, what it generates as an output, along with information about the training data and how the model has been evaluated. Model cards exist in various formats, including JSON schemas, markdown files, HTML or even Word and PDF files.

Similar to model cards, data cards also provide information about a dataset to users to add transparency to a model training pipeline. A typical dataset card may include information about the dataset’s name, its authors, intended use, details about provenance and collection, transformations and more.

In this report, we compare three model card and data card formats. The selected metadata storing and presentation formats are compatible with the FAID (Fair AI Development)¹ package which contains a logging unit to output fairness testing results to various model card formats. It is useful to know which formats are interoperable and where, in order to correctly output the testing results to the correct entities within the different model card formats.

¹ <https://github.com/asabuncuoglu13/faid>

Google Model Card

The first model card format we look at is the Model Card Toolkit (MCT) by Google [4] (Note: The toolkit is deprecated on Sep 27, 2024, however, the format is still used by Google and TensorFlow-based libraries). This toolkit is a Python package which automates the generation of a model card. The toolkit populates a template JSON schema which is then used to generate an HTML document which acts as the model card. A sample HTML document generated by MCT can be seen in Figure 1, taken directly from the MCT GitHub repository.

Figure 1 - Sample HTML output from MCT, found from the GitHub: <https://github.com/tensorflow/model-card-toolkit/tree/main>. It highlights an overview of the model, in this case a model used to predict the income of an adult based on various features. It tells us which dataset has been used and the use cases, limitations and ethical considerations connected to using this model. The user can choose to provide metrics about both the model and dataset itself, as shown by the plots. These plots are submitted by the user.

Below is a tabulated summary of the JSON. For example, for 'model_details.name', 'name' is the property of the parent class 'model_details' and so on.

Table 1 - Summarised and tabulated JSON schema for MCT, containing all entities in the schema and their descriptions. The schema can be found here: https://github.com/tensorflow/model-card-toolkit/blob/main/model_card_toolkit/schema/v0.0.2/model_card.schema.json

Property Name	Description
schema_version	The version of the schema.
model_details	Metadata about the model.
model_parameters	Parameters for the construction of the model.
quantitative_analysis	A quantitative analysis of the model.
considerations	Considerations regarding the model.
model_details.name	The name of the model.
model_details.overview	A brief, one-line description of the model card.
model_details.documentation	A thorough description of the model and its usage.
model_details.owners	The individuals or teams who own the model.
model_details.version	The version of the model.
model_details.licenses	The model's license for use.
model_details.references	Links providing more information about the model.
model_details.citations	How to reference this model card.
model_details.path	The path where the model is stored.
model_parameters.model_architecture	The architecture of the model.
model_parameters.data	The datasets used to train and evaluate the model.
model_parameters.input_format	The data format for inputs to the model.
model_parameters.input_format_map	The data format for inputs, in key-value format.
model_parameters.output_format	The data format for outputs from the model.
model_parameters.output_format_map	The data format for outputs, in key-value format.
quantitative_analysis.performance_metrics	The model performance metrics being reported.
quantitative_analysis.graphics	Graphics associated with the quantitative analysis.
considerations.users	Who are the intended users of the model?
considerations.use_cases	What are the intended use cases of the model?
considerations.limitations	Known technical limitations of the model.
considerations.tradeoffs	Known tradeoffs in accuracy/performance.
considerations.ethical_considerations	Ethical risks involved in the application of this model.
owner.name	The name of the owner.
owner.contact	The contact information of the owner.
version.name	The name of the version.
version.date	The date the version was released.
version.diff	The changes from the previous version.
license.identifier	A standard SPDX license identifier or "proprietary".
license.custom_text	The text of a custom license.

The schema contains the usual information about the model, such as a description, link to documentation, parameters, architecture etc. It also allows the user to give information about the datasets (separate from an independent data card) used to train the model along with space for graphics allowing readers to easily visualise the model's metrics. This is particularly important when using potentially biased datasets, it allows the user to potentially add a fairness assessment within the model card itself, including comments and instructions from the authors.

Hugging face Model Card

The next model card template we will look at is that of Hugging Face. A Hugging Face model card can be found in the model repository within the README.md file with a YAML section detailing the metadata about the model. Unlike MCT, the YAML file is manually constructed using the template found in the Hugging Face GitHub repository² with details and definitions found on the Hugging Face Annotated Model Card Template webpage³. Below we have summarised the entities like the MCT, including the section heading along with any properties that come underneath.

Table 2 - Entities found in the Hugging Face model card format. Whilst the properties appear as a JSON file in the MCT, they appear within a markdown file for Hugging Face. "BRL" refers to "Bias, Risks and Limitations".

Property Name	Description
Model Name: model_id	Unique identifier for the model.
Model Name: model_summary	A brief 1-2 sentence description of the model.
Model Details: model_description	Overview of the model's architecture, version, creators, and training procedures.
Model Details: developers	List of people or organizations that developed the model.
Model Details: funded_by	Funding sources for the model.
Model Details: shared_by	Optional: Individuals or organizations sharing the model.
Model Details: model_type	Type of model (e.g., supervised learning, modality).
Model Details: language	Languages the model supports (if applicable).
Model Details: license	Licensing details (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0).
Model Details: base_model	Optional: Indicates if the model is fine-tuned from another base model.
Model Details: repo, Model Details: paper, Model Details: demo	Sources: Repository link, research paper, and demo (optional).
Uses: direct_use	Explanation of how the model can be used directly, with examples.
Uses: downstream_use	Description of how the model can be fine-tuned for other tasks.
Uses: out_of_scope_use	Foreseeable misuse cases and limitations.
BRL: bias_risks_limitations	Known or potential biases, risks, and technical limitations.
BRL: bias_recommendations	Recommendations to mitigate biases and risks.
Training Details: training_data	Description of training data, with links to Dataset Cards if applicable.
Training Details: preprocessing	Information about preprocessing steps such as tokenization or resizing.
Training Details: speeds_sizes_times	Details about training speed, size, and time.

²

https://github.com/huggingface/huggingface_hub/blob/main/src/huggingface_hub/templates/modelcard_template.md

³ <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/model-card-annotated>

Evaluation: evaluation_data	Data used for evaluating the model.
Evaluation: metric	Metrics used in evaluation.
Evaluation: results	Summary of evaluation results.
Environmental Impact: emissions	Details about the model's carbon footprint or energy usage.
More Information: citations	References or citations for the model.
More Information: glossary	Definitions of key terms related to the model.
More Information: contact	Contact information for inquiries about the model.

meta-llama **Llama-3.2-3B-Instruct** like 685 Follow Meta Llama 9,772

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meta llama-3 conversational text-generation-inference Inference Endpoints arxiv:2204.05149

arxiv:2405.16406 License: llama3.2

Train Deploy Use this model

Model card Files Community 40

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```

metadata
language:
- en
- de
- fr
- it
- pt
- hi
- es
- th
library_name: transformers
pipeline_tag: text-generation
tags:
- facebook
- meta
- pytorch
- llama

```

Figure 2 - Example model on Hugging Face for the Llama-3.2B-Instruct model, found here: <https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.2-3B-Instruct/blob/main/README.md>. The model card is found under Files within the README.md file. At the top there is a YAML file containing metadata about the model.

Looking through the model card for Llama-3.2 3B Instruct [ref], the required entities from the Hugging Face model card template provides a plethora of information about the model. A common theme among Hugging Face model cards is the inclusion of sample code, as seen in Figure 3. The example code would fall under the entity “Uses.direct_use” or “Model Details.demo”, and there is further room to provide links to more documentation or links to the repository where the model is stored. MCT does provide an entity for model documentation, but not one for example code within the model card itself. This allows users with less technical expertise to quickly run inference using the models.

Use with transformers

Starting with transformers >= 4.43.0 onward, you can run conversational inference using the Transformers pipeline abstraction or by leveraging the Auto classes with the generate() function.

Make sure to update your transformers installation via pip install --upgrade transformers.

```
import torch
from transformers import pipeline

model_id = "meta-llama/Llama-3.2-3B-Instruct"
pipe = pipeline(
    "text-generation",
    model=model_id,
    torch_dtype=torch.bfloat16,
    device_map="auto",
)
messages = [
    {"role": "system", "content": "You are a pirate chatbot who always responds"},
    {"role": "user", "content": "Who are you?"},
]
outputs = pipe(
    messages,
    max_new_tokens=256,
)
print(outputs[0]["generated_text"][-1])
```

Note: You can also find detailed recipes on how to use the model locally, with torch.compile(), assisted generations, quantised and more at [huggingface-llama-recipes](#)

Figure 3 - Example code is provided within the model card itself (outside of the documentation).

Additional Model Card Formats

Amazon SageMaker AI is a managed service provided by Amazon Web Services (AWS) which provides a platform for building, training, deploying and scaling machine learning and AI solutions. It provides a model card template which is filled out through a Python SDK⁴ and contains many of the same entities as the MCT and Hugging Face formats. The user inputs information about the model and the SDK automatically creates the model card.

```
model_overview = ModelOverview.from_model_name(
    model_name=model_name,
    sagemaker_session=sagemaker_session,
    model_description="A-description-of-your-model",
    problem_type="Problem-type", # For example, "Binary Classification"
    algorithm_type="Algorithm-type", # For example, "Logistic Regression"
    model_creator="Name-of-model-creator",
    model_owner="Name-of-model-owner",
)
```

⁴ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/sagemaker/latest/dg/model-cards-create.html>

```

model_card_name = "my-model-card"
my_card = ModelCard(
    name=model_card_name,
    status=ModelCardStatusEnum.DRAFT,
    model_overview=model_overview,
    training_details=training_details,
    intended_uses=intended_uses,
    evaluation_details=evaluation_details,
    additional_information=additional_information,
    sagemaker_session=sagemaker_session,
)
my_card.create()

```

Figure 4 - SageMaker Python SDK for model card creation. The user updates variables consisting of information about the model, which are then used to create the model card.

VerifyML⁵ is an open-source toolkit designed for automating the generation of model cards, allowing users to input information through a GUI and exporting the model card as HTML files. It is also possible to generate the model cards using the python toolkit. It is an extension of the MCT and provides a greater focus on fairness and explainability. The entities appear in a JSON schema which is largely identical with MCT, with additional entities for fairness and explainability. This can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3 - The first few entities of the JSON schema found on the VerifyML Github, containing the same entities as the MCT with additional explainability and fairness entities. https://github.com/cylynx/verifyml/blob/main/verifyml/model_card_toolkit/schema/v0.0.4/model_card.schema.json

Property Name	Description
schema_version	The version of the schema.
model_details	Metadata about the model.
model_parameters	Parameters for the construction of the model.
quantitative_analysis	A quantitative analysis of the model.
considerations	Considerations regarding the model.
explainability_analysis	Explainability analysis being reported.
fairness_analysis	Fairness analysis being reported.

The extra considerations can be inputted in various places including the general “Considerations” section where the authors can summarise potential fairness harms and mitigation strategies or within their own sections where the authors can provide graphical information, such as charts highlighting the FPRs across different groups.

The Algorithmic Transparency Recording Standard

The Algorithmic Transparency Recording Standard (ATRS) is a framework for capturing information about algorithmic tools including AI systems⁶ developed by the Department for Science, Innovation

⁵ <https://www.verifyml.com/>

⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/guidance-for-organisations-using-the-algorithmic-transparency-recording-standard/algorithmic-transparency-recording-standard-guidance-for-public-sector-bodies>

and Technology (DSIT) and Central Digital and Data Office (CDDO) branches of the UK Government⁷. The ATRS provides a template in the form of an Excel spreadsheet including many of the same entities and fields as with the MCT and Hugging Face formats. It separates the information into two tiers, with “Tier 1” providing a brief overview and “Tier 2” highlighting more detailed information. The template outlines properties for both models and datasets but mentions data cards as optional.

Comparison of Documentation Formats

The MCT and Hugging Face formats allow developers to highlight information about models used in a variety of different tasks, such as language models for text generation. They allow individual practitioners to understand the use cases and limitations of the model they are using, for their individual use cases. In contrast, the ATRS is most relevant to algorithms in automated decision making (as opposed to image or text generation, for example), where the model’s output could have a direct or indirect effect on the general public⁸. This is perhaps why the data card entries are marked as optional as the focus is for recording information regarding a decision-making framework.

In summary, the MCT and Hugging Face formats both provide the opportunity for developers to provide detailed information about their models. The MCT as a package allows for the automatic generation of a model card in a HTML format, allowing for information and graphics to be presented in an easily readable format. The Hugging Face format requires manual construction of a YAML file, which is then displayed with the model on the Hugging Face repository. The ATRS is an Excel spreadsheet offering the same entities as the other formats but seeks to provide transparency to models used in automated decision making.

For the MCT, Hugging Face and ATRS formats and compared their interoperability by matching together similar entities. In the case where a format has a unique property we have listed them separately. The table can be viewed in the Appendix. In some cases, entities between the formats are clearly matching, i.e. referring to the same information, but in some cases, the matching can be more subjective. For example, the MCT has an entity “model_details.name” and Hugging Face has a property “Model Name”, obviously these will match. In some instances, the wording is slightly different although both entities refer to the same thing, and in some cases the entity can encapsulate multiple different things, i.e. one entity may refer to many entities between two formats, or vice versa, where one format may provide more granularity. The ATRS format has the most unique entities, i.e. entities which do not appear to match with the ones found in the MCT and Hugging Face formats which

⁷ <https://rtau.blog.gov.uk/2024/03/07/algorithmic-transparency-recording-standard-getting-ready-for-adoption-at-scale/>

⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/guidance-for-organisations-using-the-algorithmic-transparency-recording-standard>

is likely due to the more specialised use case which focusses on automated decision making as opposed to general AI and ML models.

Data Card Formats

Like model cards, data cards are structured documents which highlight the most important aspects of a dataset, including information about how the data is collected, what the rationale was behind its creation, its use case(s) and limitations, along with technical details including formatting, transformations and descriptive statistics. Some data card formats may also include information about bias and sensitive attributes.

The Data Cards Playbook data card template is authored by People + AI Research (PAIR) team at Google [5]. The template is offered in different formats including markdown, and as PDF and Word files which can be downloaded from the Data Cards Playbook GitHub⁹. It is motivated by 15 main themes which highlight the dataset production life cycle and are tabulated below:

Table 4 - The main sections highlighted in the PAIR data card template, which a short description/summary of the information required. The main themes can be found at: <https://sites.research.google/datacardsplaybook/> and the markdown file highlighting all classes and entities can be found at: <https://github.com/PAIR-code/datacardsplaybook/blob/main/templates/DataCardsExtendedTemplate.md>

Section heading	Description
Summary	A short summary describing the dataset, includes link to dataset and names of authors
Authorship	Details regarding authorship, organisations, contact details and funding sources
Dataset Overview	Dataset snapshot (e.g. size of dataset, number of classes etc.), overview of any sensitive data, descriptive statistics, versioning and maintenance
Example of Data Points	Primary data modality (e.g. image, text, tabular, etc), examples of typical and atypical data points
Motivations & Intentions	Purpose of dataset (e.g. research), domains of application, intended use, suitable and unsuitable use cases
Access, Retention & Wipeout	Access type (e.g. restricted, open source, etc.), links to access
Provenance	Collection methods, collection methodology, source descriptions, cadence, processing, collection criteria, version and maintenance
Human and Other Sensitive Attributes	Sensitive human attributes (e.g. gender, language, age etc.), distributions of potentially sensitive attributes

⁹ <https://github.com/PAIR-code/datacardsplaybook/tree/main/templates>

Extended Use	Safety level (e.g. safe to use with other data or not), known safe and unsafe datasets or types, best practices, limitations and recommendations
Transformations	Applied transformations (e.g. anomaly detection, data aggregation etc.), methods used
Annotations and Labeling	Workforce type (e.g. Human, machine generated, etc.), annotation characteristics and distributions
Validation Types	Methods for validation, breakdown (e.g. number of data points validated), description of human validators (e.g. languages, locations, genders)
Sampling Methods	Methods for sampling (e.g. clustering, random etc.), characteristics, criteria
Known Applications & Benchmarks	ML applications (e.g. classification, object detection), evaluation results (e.g. accuracy, precision), evaluation processes, descriptions and statistics (e.g. the model used and its model card)
Terms of Art	Concepts and definitions used in this data card
Reflections on Data	Generic notes to be added

The authors mention the following stages in the dataset life cycle; Origins, Factuals, Transformations, Experience, n=1 (examples), abbreviated as “OFTEn”. These then motivate the main themes used in the data card template, allowing users to highlight information at each stage of the dataset life cycle. The OFTEEn framework aims to provide a consistent and repeatable approach to identify and add themes from dataset life cycles. To this end, the template intends for the user to provide highly detailed information about their dataset, containing many entities within each main theme. Similar to the formats which display model cards as HTML pages, the PAIR data card format can illustrate visual information such as figures and charts.

Croissant

Structured data annotation formats such as schema.org exist for efficient parsing of web pages by search engines. Croissant is a metadata format designed specifically for ML datasets as a part of the MLCommons project¹⁰, developed collaboratively by teams from Google, Kaggle, Dataset Search and various academic institutions. Croissant aims to not only aid in data discoverability like the standard metadata formats for web pages, but also include metadata which provides insights to the characteristics of the data in a ML context and the ability to extract and combine data from different sources [6]. The format is interoperable across different frameworks; datasets with Croissant

¹⁰ <https://mlcommons.org/2024/12/croissant-medium-post/>

metadata can be loaded into TensorFlow, PyTorch and JAX using TensorFlow Datasets. The format is supported by Kaggle, Hugging Face and OpenML¹¹.

Like how the PAIR data card format is based on 15 main themes which should be captured in a data card, Croissant is organised into layers, namely: 1) Dataset Metadata layer, which contains general information, 2) Resources layer, which describes the source data, 3) Structure layer, which describes the data type and 4) Semantic layer, which describes how the data is used in ML specific domains, e.g. train/test splits.

The Croissant metadata can be generated using the Croissant editor¹² or through the open-source Python library¹³. The default namespace for objects is built from schema.org although the user is able to select from Dublin Core terms and The Wikidata name space also. A summary of the objects and their properties is found in Table 5.

Table 5 - A brief summary of the main objects and their properties, used in the Croissant metadata JSON-LD. Accessed from <https://docs.mlcommons.org/croissant/docs/croissant-spec.html>

Property/Object	Description
@context	Defines the JSON-LD namespace
@type	Describes the type of entity as text
conformsTo	Declaration that the dataset conforms to the versioned schema
name	Name of the dataset
description	Description of the dataset
license	License of the dataset
url	Link to the dataset's webpage
creator	Creator(s) of the dataset
datePublished	The date of publication
keywords	Keywords associated with the dataset
publisher	The publisher of the dataset
version	The version of the dataset
dateCreated	Initial creation date of the dataset
dateModified	Last modification date of the dataset
sameAs	Other web sources for the same dataset
sdLicence	A license document for the data
inLanguage	The language(s) of the data
isLiveDataset	If the dataset is live
citeAs	Citation for the dataset
distribution	A downloadable form of this dataset at a specific location in a specific format
FileObject	Represents individual files that are part of the dataset, properties include name, contentUrl,

¹¹ <https://research.google/blog/croissant-a-metadata-format-for-ml-ready-datasets/>

¹² <https://huggingface.co/spaces/MLCommons/croissant-editor>

¹³ <https://github.com/mlcommons/croissant>

	contentSize, encodingFormat, sameAs, sha256, containedIn
FileSet	Represents data where each file needs to be treated as an individual item. Properties include containedIn, includes and excludes (glob patterns which specify which files to include or exclude)
RecordSet	Describes a set of structured records obtained from one or more data sources expressed as fields. Properties include field (e.g. a column in a table), key, data, examples
Field	Represents a column or data element within a RecordSet. Properties include source, dataType, repeated, equivalentProperty, references, subField, parentField
DataSource	Describes the data that can be extracted from files to populate a RecordSet. Properties include fileObject, fileSet, recordSet, extract, transform, format
Extract	Specifies how the data is extracted from the source in the case where not all of the source data is needed
transform	Specifies a transformation to apply to the extracted data
format	A format string used to parse values from a DataSource

Croissant essentially adds a metadata layer to the data itself, allowing search engines to more efficiently access the data and for users to load, interact and interpret data through the platforms they wish to use. In slight contrast, data formats such as PAIR are independent documents which can be accessed where the datasets themselves are stored such as Hugging Face or GitHub repositories. As these data cards are not limited to JSON-LD, it allows authors to potentially include more detailed and nuanced information about their dataset, including descriptive statistics and information about bias and sensitive attributes, which would otherwise be difficult to interpret without graphics.

The Croissant RAI specification¹⁴ is an extension of the Croissant metadata format for datasets. It highlights information according to 7 use cases: The data life cycle, Data labelling, Participatory data, AI safety and fairness evaluation, Traceability, regulatory compliance and Inclusion. These additional considerations on top of the standard metadata format to add a greater layer of transparency with regards to bias, fairness and safety.

¹⁴ <https://docs.mlcommons.org/croissant/docs/croissant-rai-spec.html>

Within the appendix there is a comparison between the PAIR, Croissant and ATRS formats. The methodology used to match the entities is the same as that which was used for the model card comparison, where any singular or unique entities are listed at the bottom. From this comparison we can see how Croissant is unique in terms of its use case where many entities are related to discoverability, but we have also listed some entities from the RAI extension which results in the format following closer to the PAIR and ATRS formats especially in terms of bias, fairness and risk.

Final Remarks

Whilst all the formats we have examined aim to aid in the transparency of models and datasets, their use cases, limitations, technical details and more, some have differing use cases in and of themselves. Of them, the MCT and Hugging Face formats appear to be most similar both in the entities within the formats but also their use case, which is to provide transparency to models whilst being agnostic to the models down stream use case. The ATRS format, whilst demanding similar entities, focusses on models used for automated decision making. As for data cards, PAIR is the most generic with its use case being for transparency which is also the case with the Croissant format. The latter, however, aims to also enable the discoverability of datasets and the use of datasets across different development frameworks; it is not only a tool for highlighting information about data but also a tool for the responsible use of datasets. That being said, PAIR is similar to the MCT for models, in the sense that it allows for detailed information and visualisation of information to be given to the user.

References

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Appendix

Table 6 - comparison between the MCT, Hugging Face and ATRS model card formats. We used the MCT JSON schema as the default and matched all similar entities from the Hugging Face and ATRS formats accordingly. In some cases there are some matching entities only between the Hugging Face and ATRS formats which appear at the bottom of the table. Below these are the entities which are unique only to Hugging Face and ATRS. In some cases one entity from one format may represent multiple entities from another, or vice versa.

MCT		Hugging Face		ATRS		
Entity	Parent	Entity	Parent	ID	Entity	Parent
description	properties.model_details					
properties.name.description	properties.model_details			0.11/1.1/2.4.2.1	Title/Name/Model name	Metadata/Tier 1/Model
properties.overview.description	properties.model_details	model_description	Model Description	0.15/1.2/2.2.1	Description/Detailed description	Metadata/Tier 1/Description
properties.documentation.description	properties.model_details	get_started_code/glossary	Model/Glossary optional	1.3	Website URL	Tier 1
properties.owners.description	properties.model_details	developers	Model Description	0.12	Organisation name	Metadata
properties.version	properties.model_details					
properties.licenses.description	properties.model_details	license	Model Description			
properties.references.description	properties.model_details	get_started_code/glossary	Model/Glossary optional	0.15/1.2/2.2.1	Description/Detailed description	Metadata/Tier 1/Description
properties.citations.description	properties.model_details					
properties.path.description	properties.model_details					
description	properties.model_parameters			2.4.1.1/2.4.2.6	System architecture/Model architecture	Tool/Model
properties.model_architecture	properties.model_parameters	model_specs	Technical Specifications optional	2.4.1.1/2.4.2.6	System architecture/Model architecture	Tool/Model
properties.data.description	properties.model_parameters	training_data/testing_data	Training Details	2.4.2.8/2.4.2.9/2.4.3.4	Datasets/Dataset purposes/Data quantities	Model/Data
properties.input_format	properties.model_parameters	preprocessing/sizes_times	Training Details	2.4.2.4	Model input	Model
properties.input_format_map	properties.model_parameters			2.4.2.4	Model input	Model
properties.output_format	properties.model_parameters			2.4.2.5	Model output	Model

output_format_map	properties.model_parameters			2.4.2.5	Model output	Model
description	properties.quantitative_analysis	testing_factors	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics	2.4.2.7	Model performance	Model
properties.performance_metrics	properties.quantitative_analysis	testing_metrics	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics	2.4.2.7	Model performance	Model
description	properties.considerations	hardware_requirements/compute_infrastructure	Technical Specifications optional			
properties.description	properties.considerations	direct_use/downstream_use/out_of_scope_use	Uses			
properties.use_cases	properties.considerations	direct_use/downstream_use/out_of_scope_use	Uses	2.2.2	Scope	Description
properties.limitations	properties.considerations	hardware_requirements/compute_infrastructure	Technical Specifications optional			
properties.tradeoffs	properties.considerations					
properties.ethical_considerations	properties.considerations	hardware_type/hours_used/cloud_provider/cloud_region/co2_emitted	Environmental Impact			
properties.name.description	definitions.owner	model_card_owners	Model Card Authors optional	2.11-2.14		
properties.contact.description	definitions.owner	model_card_contact	Model Card Contact	1.4	Contact email	Tier 1
description.description	definitions.version			2.4.1.2/2.4.2.2	Phase/Model version	Tool/Model
properties.name.description	definitions.version			2.4.1.2/2.4.2.2	Phase/Model version	Tool/Model
properties.date.description	definitions.version			2.4.1.2/2.4.2.2	Phase/Model version	Tool/Model
properties.diff.description	definitions.version			2.4.1.2/2.4.2.2	Phase/Model version	Tool/Model
properties.identifier	definitions.version			2.4.1.3	Maintenance	Tool
custom_text.description	definitions.license					
properties.reference.description	definitions.license					
properties.description	definitions.reference					
properties.citation	definitions.citation	citation_bibtex/citation_apa	Citation optional			
properties.description	definitions.citation					
properties.value	definitions.keyval					
	definitions.keyval					

properties.description	definitions.dataset	training_data/testing_data	Training Details	2.4.3.1	Source data name	Data
link.description	definitions.dataset	training_data/testing_data	Training Details	2.4.3.7/2.4.3.10/2.4.3.11	Source data URL/Data sharing agreements/Data access and storage	Data
sensitive_graphics	definitions.dataset	bias_risks_limitations	Bias, Risks and Limitations	2.4.3.5	Sensitive Attributes	Data
description.description	definitions.dataset	training_data/testing_data	Training Details	2.4.3.2/2.4.3.3/2.4.3.6/2.4.3.8/2.4.3.9	Data modality/Data description/Data C&R/Data collection/Data cleaning	Data
properties.description	definitions.performance_metric	testing_metrics	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
value.description	definitions.performance_metric	results/results_summary	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
slice.description	definitions.performance_metric	testing_data	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
confidence_interval.description	definitions.performance_metric	testing_metrics	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
confidence_interval.properties.lower_bound.description	definitions.performance_metric	testing_metrics	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
confidence_interval.properties.upper_bound.description	definitions.performance_metric	testing_metrics	Testing Data, Factors and Metrics			
properties.sensitive_data.description	definitions.sensitive_data	bias_risks_limitations	Bias, Risks and Limitations	2.4.3.5	Sensitive attributes	Data
properties.description	definitions.graphics_collection					
properties.collection.description	definitions.graphics_collection					
properties.name.description	definitions.graphic					
properties.image.description	definitions.graphic					
properties.description	definitions.user	direct_use/downstream_use/out_of_scope_use	Uses	0.14	Region	Metadata
properties.description	definitions.use_case	direct_use/downstream_use/out_of_scope_use	Uses			
properties.description	definitions.limitation	bias_risks_limitations	Bias, Risks and Limitations			
properties.description	definitions.tradeoff					

properties.name.description	definitons.risk	bias_risks_limitations	Bias, Risks and Limitations	2.5.2	Risks and mitigations	Risks
properties.mitigation_strategy.description	definitions.risk	bias_recommendations	Bias, Risks and Limitations			
		funded_by	Model Description			
		shared_by	Model Description	2.4.1.4	Model type	Tool
		model_type	Model Description			
		language	Model Description			
		base_model	Model Description			
		repo/paper/demo	Model Sources			
		model_examination	Model Examination optional Technical Specifications optional			
		software	optional	0.13	Phase	Metadata
				2.2.3	Benefit	Description
				2.2.4	Previous process Alternatives considered	Description
				2.2.5		Description
				2.3.1	Process integration	Decisions
				2.3.1	Provided information	Decisions
				2.3.4	Human decisions and review	Decisions
				2.3.5	Required training	Decisions
				2.3.6	Appeals and review	Decisions
				2.5.1	Impact assessment	Risks

Table 7 - comparison of PAIR, Croissant and ATRS formats for data cards. Similar to the model card comparison, we start with the PAIR format as the default and then match similar entities from Croissant and ATRS, leaving the unique entities at the bottom of the table. Once again there is a 1:N cardinality between some entities and others, and vice versa. For the Croissant specification, we have included some entities from the RAI (responsible AI) extension, which focusses on safety, bias and risk. These entities begin with rai: as the namespace. Note, not all entities from the RAI specification are added due to their granularity, e.g. adding entities for “annotation protocol” and “annotation platform” is not required for our comparison purposes, just listing there is scope for information about annotation within the format is sufficient.

PAIR Data Card	Croissant	ATRS
Property	Property	Property
Summary	name	Dataset name, Dataset description
Authorship	creator, publisher, citeAs	Dataset creator, Dataset owner, Contact details, Data card author
Dataset Overview	description, license, version, dateCreated, dateModified, datePublished, inLanguage	Data modality, size of dataset, Number of samples, Number of attributes, Data subjects, Language, Time, Geographical coverage
Example of Data Points	Format, rai:CollectionMissingData	Number of data points, Missing data points
Motivations & Intentions	Rai:dataUseCases	Data collection purpose
Access, Retention & Wipeout	url, distribution	Dataset access, Dataset access prerequisites
Provenance	DataSource, rai:dataCollection	Data collection purpose, Data collection cadence, Data source descriptions
Human and Other Sensitive Attributes	Rai:personalSensitiveInformation, rai:dataBiases	Sensitive fields, Data representativeness
Extended Use		
Transformations	transform, Extract, rai:dataManipulationProtocol, rai:PreprocessingProtocol	Data collection and processing methods
Annotations and Labelling	Format, rai:dataAnnotationProtocol	Data collection and processing methods
Validation Types		Data collection and processing methods
Sampling Methods		Data collection and processing methods
Known Applications & Benchmarks		
Terms of Art		
Reflections on Data		
	context	
	type	
	conforms to	
	keywords	
	sameAs	
	sdlicense	
	isLiveDataset	
	FileObject	
	FileSet	
	RecordSet	
	Field	